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THE PRINCIPLE OF LOYALTY IN POLISH CIVIL LAW PROCEEDINGS**

Abstract: *The principle of loyalty in Polish civil law proceedings tends to be unjustly neglected in doctrine and jurisprudence alike. Pursuant to Article 3 of the Polish Code of Civil Procedure (CCP), “parties to and participants in proceedings shall be obliged to engage in procedural steps in conformity to generally accepted good practices, elucidate the facts of any case truthfully and without concealing any circumstance, and produce evidence as required”. This provision is the source of the principle of truthfulness, one of the primary dogmas in Polish civil law proceedings. The principle of truthfulness has been duly described in multiple monographs, papers, and scientific conferences. The legislator has also enshrined an obligation for parties to and participants in proceedings to act with mutual loyalty. The scope of loyalty-related duties extends to mutual conduct of the parties and parties’ conduct towards the judiciary. Since the judiciary is not listed as an addressee of the previously mentioned norm, a literal interpretation would suggest that courts of law are not bound by any loyalty duties towards parties to proceedings. A failure of the judiciary to show loyalty to parties to proceedings is frequent in Polish civil law proceedings. On the other hand, the principle of mandatory co-operation among parties, plenipotentiaries, and the judiciary – the principle of loyalty – is the first one to have been listed in the ELI/UNIDROIT Model European Rules of Civil Procedure. In consideration of solutions employed by certain other states, the author of this paper ponders herein whether the CCP should introduce the principle of loyalty expressis verbis and, if so, in what form.*

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1. Introduction

Dictionaries define *loyalty* as reliability and fidelity in dealings with others. In the *Polish Scientific Publishing House (PWN) Encyclopaedia*, the term carries three meanings:

- 1) the moral attitude of constant behaviour towards a specific individual, whether in his/her presence or absence; the above applies to family and friends in particular;
- 2) acting in conformity to commitments made (e.g. to an employer), or to the letter of law; civic loyalty; and
- 3) righteousness, fidelity, reliability in dealings with others (PWN Encyclopaedia, n.d.).¹

Deliberations articulated herein will apply in particular to the meaning listed under item 2). In the context of judicial proceedings, one ought to consider whether citizens and other entities recognised as parties thereto ought to be the only ones bound with loyalty (and whom they ought to be loyal to when taking action themselves), and should loyalty in action not be expected of courts of law as well.

The principle of loyalty in Polish civil law proceedings tends to be unjustly neglected in doctrine and jurisprudence alike. Rarely mentioned, no academic textbook lists it among the guiding principles of civil law proceedings.

2. The principle of loyalty in Polish substantive civil law

The principle of loyalty has a long-standing tradition in Polish substantive law. The Polish Civil Code (hereinafter referred to as: the CC), passed in 1964 (numerous fundamental² amendments thereto notwithstanding), has since day one included an injunction for creditors to co-operate with debtors loyally when discharging any duties (Article 354 of the CC).

Loyalty-related responsibilities apply to contractual obligations as well as those sourced in acts of law, judicial rulings, or even unilateral legal acts

¹ PWN Encyclopaedia (n.d.). "Lojalność". In: Polish Scientific Publishing House (PWN) Encyclopaedia. Retrieved 5 April 2024 from <https://encyklopedia.pwn.pl/haslo/lojalnosc;4009038.html>

² It was particularly profound after the 1989 collapse of communism in Poland.

obligatory in nature. The doctrine correctly assumes that the principle of loyalty under civil law shall extend to labour law as well; consequently, the employee shall thereunder be obliged to remain loyal to the employer, having shouldered a number of responsibilities (Suknarowska-Drzewiecka, 2001: 587-591).

Pursuant to Article 354 §1 of the CC, the debtor shall be obliged to perform under any and all obligations in conformity to their substance, in a form and manner consistent with their social and economic purpose, rules of social co-existence, and commonly accepted customs, if any. Article 354 § 2 provides that this is also how the creditor shall co-operate with the debtor whenever acting on an obligation. While the aforesaid debtor- and creditor-related regulation is fundamentally symmetrical for both parties concerned, the legislator has also made the creditor responsible for taking certain action and collaborating with the debtor to an extent short of which collecting on the obligation by the debtor would be either impossible or considerably (excessively) challenging.³ The purpose of the aforesaid regulation is to secure a contractual equilibrium for both parties concerned (Safjan, 2007: 299-300).

It follows that the fundamental responsibility of the debtor is to perform honestly under the obligation at hand, whereas the fundamental responsibility of the creditor is to co-operate with the debtor. Said co-operation ought to apply to all and any duties of the debtor recognised as contributing to the underlying obligation. The purpose of aforesaid responsibility extends beyond the co-operating creditor seeking compensation or acting in their own interest only. Nonetheless, this does not exhaust the beneficial outcomes of creditors taking action to co-operate. A trustworthy creditor shall co-operate to allow both parties to an agreement to perform honestly, and in conformity to its provisions: a trustworthy debtor shall intend to perform under the commitment undertaken and have themselves released from the obligation. A trustworthy debtor wishes to cease being a debtor. Consequently, the creditor's duty to co-operate with the debtor in the spirit of loyalty serves the purpose of safeguarding and securing justified interests of both parties to a contractual obligation (Warkało, 1973: 43-57).

It is rather easy to imagine the complications, should a creditor be unwilling to co-operate with the debtor (e.g. by refusing to collect goods from the debtor, failing to respond to his/her refusal to provide a bank account number for debt repayment purposes). This is why certain creditor responsibilities arising from the principle of loyalty in co-operating with debtors have

³ Cf. e.g. (of the many comments in legal literature and Supreme Court case law): 1) Supreme Court ruling of 25th November 1998, case Ref. No. II CKN 60/98; 2) Supreme Court ruling of 25th February 2015, case Ref. No. IV CSK 297/14.

been further regulated in detailed Civil Code provisions. Let us assume that a purchaser is expected to collect goods from the seller, an entity contracting agricultural produce to collect said goods by a specific date. A construction works client is expected to conform to specific preparations in advance (e.g. provide the contractor with access to the construction site and construction design blueprints); furthermore, the client shall be ready for partial and/or final works acceptance, once completed. Should the contractor choose to employ subcontractors, the client shall have a say in the matter, as such solutions require the client's written consent. When ordering tailor-made work, the client shall provide the contractor with proper guidelines, and appear for measurements to be taken if necessary; should the work involve material(s) provided by the client, the client shall deliver as required.

Should a creditor fail to perform duties duly assigned, Polish law deems such creditor to be in default (Article 486 §1 of the CC); *default* is defined as a qualified and culpable delay in performing under an obligation. Default shall give rise to compensation liability. Consequently, should the creditor be found culpable of default, the debtor suffering damage as a result, the debtor shall have the right to claim compensation from the creditor. The debtor may under such circumstances discharge itself from the underlying obligation by placing the object of consideration in judicial deposit.

The creditor's loyalty-related duty to the debtor is by no means limited to actions specified by law or contract. It also involves the passive responsibility of refraining from all and any action preventing the debtor from performing under the underlying obligation, or exposing the debtor to additional expenses or to liability for delay.⁴ Not causing any obstructions to the debtor is considered the bare minimum of loyalty; any breach thereof is also recognisable as a violation to the principles of honesty and good practice in legal relations (Machnikowski, 2023).⁵ While not every agreement requires the creditor to co-operate actively, the creditor is obliged to refrain from causing obstructions to the debtor, circumstances notwithstanding (passive responsibility).

Legal doctrine may refer to active and passive responsibilities as positive and negative. Interestingly enough, the provisions in question date back to 1964, the year when the Civil Code was passed. Poland was then a state under communism, commonly referred to as "*socialism*". Instructing the debtor and creditor to co-operate, provisions of Article 354 §§ 1 and 2 of the CC were considered an indicator of "*the socialist notion of co-operation and mutual assistance*", one in principle ostensibly alien to legislative systems of

⁴ Supreme Court ruling of 18th April 2013, case Ref. No. III CSK 243/12.

⁵ See also: Supreme Court ruling of 27th March 2013, case Ref. No. V CSK 112/12.

“antagonistic societies”. As Grzegorz Klich (Klich, 2021: 217) correctly points out, similar reasoning had underpinned the adoption of the principle of cooperation between parties bound by contract in Article 1:202 of the Principles of European Contract Law (PECL).⁶ The PECL is one of the pivotal documents designed to unify private law in the European Union. It is an instrument comprising norms established pursuant to a method of comparing civil law solutions across European Union member states. Article 1:102 of the PECL introduces i.a. the principle of the parties’ freedom to enter into a contract, subject to the requirements of good faith and fair dealing. Contractual provisions cannot exclude safeguards guaranteeing acting in good faith or fair dealing. It is thus noteworthy that, both in the Polish regulation (which is older than the PECL) and in the PECL themselves, the parties’ responsibility to co-operate is closely tied in with the principle of integrity in legal relations: the duty of parties to a contractual obligation to co-operate in the spirit of loyalty forms part of a broader principle of respecting the rule of fairness in private law.

According to one of the PECL authors (Ole Lando), *“a contract shall be regarded as an instrument of co-operation, not as a confrontation of adversaries, each seeking his advantage at the expense of the other”* (Klich, 2021: 218).

3. The principle of loyalty in Polish civil procedural law

The responsibility to respect rules of fairness in private law, unquestioned in substantive law, is subjected to certain restrictions under procedural law; the adversarial principle – the basic model for judicial proceedings under civil law throughout Europe – is recognised as the primary obstacle. It goes without saying, however, that nowhere is the adversarial model *“pure”*. Assorted exceptions allowing – or outright commanding – courts of law to engage in active *ex officio* pursuits are both subjective and objective in nature. Examples include courts examining consumer contracts for abusive clauses *ex officio*, or allowing evidence *ex officio*, should one of the parties to judicial proceedings be particularly vulnerable. Restrictions to the inquisitorial system in the Polish judiciary arise from the right to (a fair) trial, secured both in the Constitution of the Republic of Poland and the European Convention on Human Rights, while exercising the principle of truth.

Pursuant to Article 3 of the Polish Code of Civil Procedure (hereinafter referred to as: the CCP), parties to and participants in proceedings are obliged

⁶ Article 1: 202: *Duty to Co-operate. Each party owes to the other a duty to co-operate in order to give full effect to the contract.* Retrieved 6 April 2024 from: https://www.trans-lex.org/400200/_/pecl/#head_12.

to seek truth and take action in conformity with the principles of truthfulness and good practice. The provision reads as follows: “*Parties to and participants in proceedings shall be obliged to engage in procedural steps in conformity to generally accepted good practices, elucidate the facts of any case truthfully and without concealing any circumstance, and produce evidence as required.*”

Doctrine and case law thus derive procedural principles of truth, adversarialism and loyalty from said provision’s content. Yet, the provision’s content offers no clear answer as to who the norm’s addressee is. The most restricted definition of the phrase “*participants in proceedings*” unquestionably suggests that they include e.g. side interveners, legal representatives, prosecutors and *pro publico bono* organisations, should a suit have been filed in the interest of a specific third party (rather than own interest). A broader definition would include witnesses, translators/interpreters and expert witnesses (authors of expert opinions serving the purpose of a given judicial procedure, or even other proceedings, should such opinions be put to use in the former). The scope of entities listed as loyalty obligation addressees is indisputable.

It is easy to interpret the provision’s literal content as suggesting that the duty of acting in conformity with the principle of loyalty is horizontal (i.e. applicable among parties to and participants in proceedings) as well as – or, possibly, primarily – vertical. Loyalty is a mandatory requirement for parties to and participants in proceedings in their dealings with the judiciary. A court of law is the “*addressee*” of procedural actions, responsible for evaluating the content of all said actions in formal and substantive terms alike. Claims and evidence are also submitted before the court as their addressee (“*da mihi factum...*”).

Yet, provisions of Article 3 of the CCP are unclear as to whether the court of law is also the addressee of the procedural loyalty commanding norm. Doctrine tends to refer to the judiciary as a body rather than participant of civil law proceedings. Linguistic (literal) interpretation of the provision (its content *per se*) seems to suggest that courts of law are not bound with any kind of loyalty-related responsibility. Nonetheless, ever since the 1997 enactment of the Constitution of the Republic of Poland, an obligation to interpret legal norms pro-constitutionally has been in force, requiring said norms to be elucidated in a manner ensuring the conformity of their application to principles, rights and freedoms safeguarded by the Constitution.

Article 2 of the Polish Constitution introduces the principle of the rule of law as the foundation of the democratic system, the doctrine and Constitutional Court deriving detailed rules therefrom. The principle of safeguard-

ing public trust in the state and law is one such rule.⁷ As duly noted by the Constitutional Court, “*while the principle in question has not been explicitly worded in the text of the Constitution, it goes without saying that it forms part of the canon of rules contributing to the concept of the rule of law in the sense afforded thereto under Article 2 of the Constitution*”.⁸ The principle of safeguarding public trust in the state and law is also referred to as the principle of a state’s loyalty to its citizens. This principle gives rise to an injunction for every state authority (the judiciary included) to treat citizens in keeping with minimum rules of fairness. This means that neither legal provisions nor action taken by aforesaid authorities can set traps or give rise to illusionary or ostensible solutions. Furthermore, state bodies shall not abuse their position in their dealings with citizens.

This is why, since the enactment of the Constitution which introduced i.a. the aforesaid principle, Article 3 of the CCP shall be interpreted as establishing an extensive duty of loyalty, applicable to the judiciary as well.

While the position has been gradually emerging in Polish case law, its visibility basically applies to a single procedural circumstance, namely in terms of refraining from taking parties to proceedings by surprise with a trial outcome, should factual grounds for the claim asserted in original action potentially justify the use of a different legal basis allowing parties to take fitting procedural steps (e.g. produce relevant evidence). Under such circumstances, the principle of loyalty requires that a party to proceedings be notified of the option to apply different legal grounds than originally suggested in positions taken by parties to proceedings, in particular the legal basis referenced by the plaintiff in the statement of claim.⁹

The question of actual loyalty-related obligation content arises, should such responsibility become binding for the judiciary. In Polish criminal law proceedings, the principle of loyalty (referred to by some authors as the principle of processual information) requires procedural bodies to instruct a participant in proceedings of his/her rights and responsibilities (Article 16 § 1 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, hereinafter: the CCrP). Furthermore, the authority conducting the proceedings (lead agency) shall, whenever justified, notify participants in proceedings of their rights and responsibilities,

⁷ For more on the origin and content of the principle, see: Justyna Węglińska, J. (2020), *Zasada ochrony zaufania obywateli do państwa i do stanowionego przez nie prawa jako dyrektywa poprawnej legislacji* (The Principle of Safeguarding Public Trust in the State and its Legislation as a Directive of Proper Legislation). *Prawo w Działaniu*. 2020/42. 171-176.

⁸ Constitutional Court ruling of 20th December 1999, case Ref. No. K 4/99.

⁹ E.g. Supreme Court resolution of 17th February 2016, case ref. No. III CZP 108/15, or the Supreme Court ruling of 20th October 2021, case Ref. No. I NSNc 45/21.

even if the law does not expressly reference such an obligation (Article 16 § 2 of the CCrP). Regardless of which of the aforesaid procedural circumstances arises, no failure to provide such instructions or defective notification shall give rise to adverse outcomes for any participant in criminal proceedings, or any other person concerned (Bojańczyk 2012: 196). Notwithstanding the above, the judiciary's responsibility to remain loyal to parties in civil proceedings shall not be restricted to a duty to notify parties as appropriate because notification-related responsibilities have been regulated under separate legal provisions. That said, a vast majority of case law proves that a failure to instruct does not constitute grounds for invalidating proceedings because such failure is not usually recognised as a breach of a civil law proceedings party's right to defence.

The aforementioned case law alone, regarding the non-admissibility of surprising parties to proceedings with novel legal grounds, suggests that loyalty is defined much more extensively, potentially referring to assorted procedural steps taken by the judiciary. In practice, however, courts all too rarely resort to their loyal co-operation duties. On the contrary: every legal representative (and every party appearing *pro se*) have frequently faced surprising, unpredictable and thus disloyal judicial action.

The time to adjudicate cases has recently been extended out of proportion in Poland.¹⁰ In a move to improve the case examination volume and swiftness of statistics, some justices are resorting to returning actions brought by professional representatives under the pretext of having identified formal defects therein.¹¹ As re-submitted actions are assigned new reference numbers, cases bearing original reference numbers are recorded as closed. Pursuant to Article 130 §1 of the CCP, a formal defect of a pleading is recognised as grounds for discontinuing proceedings. Such defects may include a missing mailing address for the defendant, a missing copy of the statement of claim for the opposing party, and/or missing powers of attorney (should action be brought by a legal representative). Online legal professionals' forums are rife with examples of grotesque grounds for having pleadings returned, while said pleadings are actually free of any defects giving rise to discontinuing proceedings. Examples include claims that powers of attorney had not been signed (as the client's signature was considered "*illegible*"), or concluding

¹⁰ A number of contributing factors can be identified, their description extending beyond the scope of this paper.

¹¹ Should formal defects be identified in action brought by a party appearing *pro se*, the court shall summon that party to remedy said defects. Conversely, should formal defects be identified in action brought by professional representatives, the court shall decide to the effect of returning the statement of claim rather than summoning the representative to remedy said effects.

that a legal representative had failed to include his/her contact information in the statement of claim, said information having been featured in the letterhead or footer rather than in the statement body proper.

Other examples of disloyalty include cases of judicial administrative offices failing to notify parties, representatives and/or witnesses of the unfeasibility of conducting a hearing according to schedule for specific reasons (such as the justice's illness). Participants in proceedings might learn of such circumstances only upon arrival on court premises, while administrative office staff might have been aware of the justice's illness for some time. Notably, should a party in proceedings take similar action by notifying the court of illness-related circumstances at the last minute while having had the option to do so earlier, jurisprudence will point to such behaviour as abuse of procedural law; the said abuse is sanctionable by having such party charged with full judicial (legal) fees, even in case that party ultimately wins the case. Other examples of disloyalty include cases of setting hearing dates and/or times in full knowledge of considerable delays to hearing openings, e.g. setting only a slightly earlier time (e.g. thirty minutes) for a preceding trial requiring a number of witnesses to be heard. In the past, an appeals court kept rejecting appeals month after month in a situation previously recognised by the Supreme Court as a circumstance disallowing appeal rejection.

Such circumstances give rise to an unpredictability of the legal situation, resulting in reduced public trust in the state and a consequent breach of Article 2 of the Polish Constitution.

4. The principle of loyalty in the ELI/UNIDROIT Model European Rules of Civil Procedure

In Polish legal sciences, the ELI/UNIDROIT Model European Rules of Civil Procedure¹² have been deservedly referred to by Andrzej Olaś as "*the most impressively advanced achievement in efforts to harmonise and modernise civil procedural law in Europe with the use of soft-law instruments*" (Olaś, 2022: 298-311).

The ELI-UNIDROIT Rules open with guiding principles of proceeding. The first listed rule is the duty to co-operate, explicitly extending to courts of law, the parties', representatives' and the judiciary.

¹² ELI-UNIDROIT Model European Rules of Civil Procedure, adopted on 15th July 2020 and 24th September 2020 by the European Law Institute Council and UNI-DROIT Governing Council; Retrieved 11 April 2024 from: <https://www.unidroit.org/instruments/civil-procedure/eli-unidroit-rules>.

SECTION 2 – Principles A. Co-operation Rule 2.

General Parties, their lawyers and the court must co-operate to promote the fair, efficient and speedy resolution of the dispute.

The principle of co-operation is supplemented by responsibilities of legal representatives and the judiciary, duly listed in two successive rules. Rule No. 4 specifies judicial responsibility:

Rule 4. Role of the Court – the General Case Management Duty. The court is responsible for active and effective case management. The court must ensure that parties enjoy equal treatment. Throughout proceedings it shall monitor whether parties and their lawyers comply with their responsibilities under these Rules.

As correctly noted by Andrzej Olaś, the principle of parties' and the court co-operation, as expressed in ELI/UNIDROIT Rules, is a flexible compromise between models differing in terms of the degree of adversarialism and judicial activeness acceptable to individual European states. It references the civil law proceedings model contemporaneously evolving in German doctrine, based on the notion of dialogue between the procedural body and entities participating in proceedings (Olaś, 2022: 304-305). Citizens should never be made to feel in court as if they were intruding.

Impacting the domestic law of multiple states to an ever-greater extent, this model law is ultimately becoming the source of appropriate reforms. Affecting European Union law, it has also been an indirect influence on the domestic legislation of EU member states (Fredriksen, Magne Strandberg, 2022: 143-157). In the age of mobility-oriented societies, nobody needs convincing that instilling greater similarities to judicial proceedings models, within the EU in particular, would be a desirable phenomenon, making legal relations considerably easier.

5. Conclusions

Interpreted i.a. as judicial duty to parties to and participants in proceedings, procedural loyalty is poorly emphasised in the Polish Code of Civil Procedure. Even if aware of the aforesaid duty, judicial practice (as revealed in case law) interprets it exceedingly narrowly, applying it in a single set of circumstances as described herein. On the other hand, a list of examples of courts acting in ways justifiably referred to as disloyal – or unpredictable at best – can be easily produced.

The President of the Research Centre of the Polish Bar Association and the Presidium of the Polish Bar Council have appointed a Team charged with

applying dogmatic and empirical research methodology in view of drafting a report showcasing Code of Civil Procedure provisions most harmful to the public, complete with proposals of appropriate amendments.¹³ *De lege ferenda* postulates proffered by the Team include an expansion of Article 3 of the CCP to include the principle of loyalty *expressis verbis* extending to courts of law. Since Article 3 of the CCP is part of a special-purpose section of the Code of Civil Procedure (“*Introductory Title. General Provisions*”), given the overall structure of said legislation, provisions ensclosed therein shall apply to the entire civil law proceedings system (Harla, 2022: 989-1020) while being recognised as axiological guidelines (Harla, 2022: 993).

Our Team believes that such amendments to Article 3 of the CCP will become a remedy for certain negative judicial behaviours (resorted to by individual justices, court administrative office staff, and judicial Customer Service Office staff). Furthermore, it will produce the desired effect of harmonisation with ELI/UNIDROIT model law.

This project was submitted to Parliament by the Polish Bar Council in July. It has since generated considerable interest both in the media and in academic circles.

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¹³The author is pleased and honoured to serve as the project’s scientific manager.

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НАЧЕЛО САВЕСНОСТИ У ПОЉСКОМ ГРАЂАНСКОМ ПОСТУПКУ

Резиме

У пољском грађанском поступку, начело савесности је недовољно заступљен у правној доктрини и судској пракси. Члан 3. пољског Закона о грађанском поступку (ЗКП) предвиђа да су странке и учесници у поступку дужни поступају у складу са правилима добре праксе и савесног поступања. Иако није експлицитно пописан законом, овај принцип има важну улогу у обезбеђивању међусобног поштовања и сарадње између странака и правосуђа. У контексту судског поступка, начело савесности представља обавезу странака да поступају на правичан и частан начин. Иако је присутно у пракси, ово начело није експлицитно наведено међу водећим принципима пољске правне доктрине. Ипак, оно је дубоко укорењено у пољском материјалном праву, посебно у контексту уговорних обавеза, где је међусобна сарадња између дужника и повериоца кључни принцип. Сврха овог принципа је да успостави равнотежу у уговорним односима и гарантује савесно понашање учесника.

У контексту грађанског процесног права, члан 3 ЗКП обухвата принцип истинитости и, сходно томе, савесности. Обим примене ове одредбе је предмет спора, посебно у погледу применљивости на судску власт и странке у спору. Бројни су примери несавесног понашања судија, као што су непредвидиво враћање тужби због мањих или непостојећих недостатака и необавештавање странака о промени термина рочишта. Таква пракса нарушава поверење јавности у правни систем.

ЕЦ/УНИДРОИТ модел Европских правила парничног поступка изричито захтева сарадњу између странака, њихових адвоката и суда како би се обезбедило правично и ефикасно решавање спорова. Овај модел је предложен као мерило за пољски закон у циљу побољшања процедуралне правичности.

Аутор овог рада предлаже измену члана 3 ЗКП којом би се експлицитно прописао принцип савесности и обавеза савесног поступања проширила на правосуђе. Циљ предложеног амандмана је повећање поверења у правни систем и усклађивање пољског законодавства са европским стандардима. Укључивањем начела савесности у ЗКП би се уклонили неки недостаци актуелне судске праксе, промовисала правичност, и ускладио пољски

грађанскоправни поступак са европским моделима. Овај амандман би могао допринети побољшању квалитета суђења и предвидивости поступања судија, чиме би се вратило поверење јавности у правни систем.

Кључне речи: *принцип савесности, принцип сарадње, парнични поступак, ELI/UNIDROIT модел Европских правила парничног поступка, Пољска.*